

REACTIONS WITH DRY ALKALINE EARTH HYDROXIDES. PART V. A SIMPLE AND RAPID METHOD FOR THE ESTIMATION OF NITROGEN, NITRIC ACID AND NITROGEN PEROXIDE CONTENTS IN METALLIC NITRATES

By J. DATTA

A metallic nitrate can be estimated for its nitrogen ingredient by heating the salt with an excess of dry lime-sulphur mixture (33% or less of sulphur), titrating the evolved ammonia and estimating the same in terms of nitrate-nitrogen, nitric acid etc. In case of nitrates other than of alkali or alkaline earth metals, a preliminary treatment of the salt with Na_2CO_3 is necessary. The merits and limitations of the process have been discussed.

It has been shown in a previous communication (this *Journal*, 1952, 29, 465) that the nitrogen of the alkali nitrate is reduced to ammonia when the salt is heated with the mixtures of any non-metal like C, S, Se, or P and any dry alkaline earth hydroxide powder; but it is only with lime-sulphur mixture containing less than 33% sulphur that the transformation to ammonia is complete. Object of the present work was to ascertain whether the said mode of reduction could be developed into a new method for the estimation of the nitrogen ingredient of metallic nitrates. Of the different methods available for the purpose, Davarda's (*Z. anal. Chem.*, 1894, 33, 113) probably is the most commonly used. In principle it depends upon the reduction of the nitrate to ammonia by the nascent hydrogen evolved by the action of metals like Zn etc. on aqueous solutions of caustic alkali.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Commercial samples of the nitrates of K, Na, Ba, Pb and Cu were first dried in desiccators for 48 hours and stored in stoppered bottles. Samples from them (0.1 g.) were analysed (according to Davarda's method, cf. Treadwell and Hall, "Analytical Chemistry", Vol. II, 5th Ed., p. 384) with the results as given below under respective heads.

In the present series of experiments the mixture for the reaction (hereafter called the "charge") was prepared as follows. The accurately weighed nitrate was put into a 60 c.c. basin and pulverised by the round end of a big test tube (1×6 inches). Requisite quantities of lime and sulphur, as given in the respective heads in the tables below, were added and the whole thoroughly mixed. The test tubes for heating the charge were of hard glass and 5×1 inches in size. A mixture containing 1 g. of lime and 3 g. of CaCl_2 was placed at the bottom of the test tube and shaken with 5 c.c. of water. The mass was allowed to solidify and then 1 g. more of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ was placed over it. A glass rod (2 mm.) was centrally pressed through the mass and the charge, as made above, was poured into the annular space. The test tube was then padded on a soft cushion so as to compress the powder inside to half the volume of the test tube. The glass rod was then withdrawn with the caution to put back all the adhering solid, and the empty space of the test tube was filled up with sodalime granules (1:2, 20 mesh powder), plugged with double fold of filter paper, and closed with a tight fitting and seamless velvet cork having a central hole through which (3"× $\frac{1}{4}$ ") glass tube was introduced, its other end being connected by a short rubber tubing with a long delivery tube (2"× $\frac{1}{4}$ ") dipping under standard HCl solution (N/10) kept in a small conical flask (60 c.c.). The test tube was arranged horizontally on a stand, the clamp fitting on the protruding portion of the cork. At first the sodalime region of the tube was heated by playing the flame, but finally placing it immediately below, in order to prevent the accumulation of any water in this region. Next, the flame of a second burner, made semiluminous and reduced to a small size, was placed about 2 inches below the region containing the charge. The test tube was occasionally rotated so as to expose all its sides to the heating action of the hot draft of air.

After about 5 minutes' slow heating the full, non-luminous flame was applied to raise the charge to a dull red heat and continued for about 5 minutes more. The flame was then carefully transferred towards the bottom of the test tube when water, expelled from the hydrated CaCl_2 , swept away all the evolved ammonia. Finally the whole of the test tube was strongly heated by manipulating both the burners till a back suction in the long test tube indicated the complete expulsion of all the volatile matters. The delivery tube was then separated and its washings added to the contents in the conical flask, care being taken to keep the volume therein always the same (about 25 c.c.), the dilution at which the original standardisation was made. The titration of the acid furnished the alkali equivalent of the ammonia formed, wherefrom the nitrate contents, and nitrogen, nitric acid etc. could be calculated as usual. Results of the first set of experiments with nitrates as such are given in Table I. In the second set, the nitrates of Cu and Pb, as were found to yield poor results by the above treatment, were dissolved, after weighing, in 2 c.c. of hot water (60 c.c. basin being heated on the burner) and 1 g. of Na_2CO_3 added to it. The mass was stirred till almost solid. The rest of the procedure was the same as before. Results obtained from these two sets of experiments are given in Tables I and II respectively.

TABLE I

Nitrate taken.	Composition of the charge			Nitrate %	
	Nitrate.	$\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$.	Sulphur.	Found.	by Davarda's.
KNO_3 ..	0.1 g	1.7 g	0.5 g	70.7	70.7
	0.2	3.4	1.0	70.2	
	0.3	5.0	1.5	68.7	
NaNO_3 ..	0.1	1.7	0.5 g	90.0	90.5
	0.2	3.4	1.0	90.0	
	0.3	5.0	1.5	89.1	
$\text{Ba}(\text{NO}_3)_2$..	0.1	1.7	0.5	80.0	80.0
	0.2	3.4	1.0	79.4	
$\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$..	0.1	1.7	0.5	89.5	92.8
$\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2$..	0.1	1.7	0.5	73.2	98.4

TABLE II

		Composition of the charge			Nitrate %	
		Nitrate.	$\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$	Sulphur.	Found	by Davarda's.
$\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$	..	0.1	1.7	0.5	92.0	92.8
$\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2$	..	0.1	1.7	0.5	97.8	98.4

DISCUSSION

Results in Table I indicate that the nitrate contents of alkali and alkaline earth nitrates, estimated by lime-sulphur method, come to be the same as by Davarda's, but in case of other nitrates the results are appreciably lower. This is probably caused by the early thermal decomposition of the salts concerned with the loss of nitrogen as NO etc., since it has been shown (Table II) that the said salts being stabilised by the addition of Na_2CO_3 , the values of the nitrate contents come almost at par with those by Davarda's. Taking this precaution in case of thermo-unstable salts, it is therefore possible to utilise the lime-sulphur method of reduction as a new process for the estimation of nitrate etc. in metallic nitrates. As compared to the standard methods, the suggested one offers several advantages: (i) it is finished rapidly, by skilled hand even within half an hour; (ii) it does not require the use of any complicated appliances or costly material; (iii) it can be undertaken in any ordinary laboratory with or without gas and water connections, since, it has been found that the use of spirit-lamp for heating and air condenser for cooling the ammoniacal vapour does not in any way interfere with the final results,

It is, however, to be noticed that the results from the lime sulphur reduction are accurate only when the weights of nitrates taken are low (preferably 0.1 g.) Even with 0.3 g. the results come about 1% lower than the standard. The cause of this is undoubtedly connected with a secondary effect, the direct reaction of sulphur and nitrate causing the loss of nitrogen in the elementary or the oxide form. The action of these very strong reactants is suppressed by the presence of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ (with proper adjustment of the proportions even below the limit of titrimetric detection since the yields of nitrogen as ammonia to the extent of 99 to 100% have been registered from the reduction of 0.1 g. of KNO_3 , vide this *Journal*, 1952, 29, 751) but cannot possibly be eliminated *in toto*. When, therefore, the weights of nitrates taken are high, the sum total of the effect becomes marked and registers a corresponding diminution in the yields of ammonia. This limitation of the process has therefore to be noted that it is not amenable to the use of such weights of nitrates with which N or $N/2$ standard solutions can be worked with. To one accustomed to the use of $N/10$ solutions the method offers little difficulty, dependable readings being obtained even from 0.1 g. of any nitrate

SRIPAT SINGH COLLEGE,
JIAGANJ.

Received October 10, 1952.